

Kinetic studies on Thionyl Chloride Fatty Acid system: Part III. Halogenation of Different Fatty Acids in Different Solvents

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Kinetic data are reported for the halogenation of acetic, propionic, butyric and valeric acids, in chloro, bromo, and nitrobenzene between 20 and 40°C. The behaviour of solvent and mechanism of the reaction has been discussed in terms of parameters of absolute reaction rate equation.

Numerous kinetic investigations have been made on the influence of solvents on reaction rate¹ and the relative importance of changes in the factors P and E of the Arrhenius equation ($PZe^{-E/RT}$). In our previous investigations² on acetic and propionic acids in xylene and xylene-dioxane mixtures, a correlation between PZ and E has been reported, which is similar to the Hawkin's³ observations for the bimolecular formation of alkyl pyridinium bromide, in different solvents.

In this communication, we present our results on the halogenation of acetic, propionic and butyric acids in polar solvents. Our previous observation² for acetic and propionic acids falls in line with our present work. A summary of the data of the previous report has been included in this communication to discuss the role of the solvent on reaction rate.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents: The chemicals used were of laboratory grade (B.D.H.), and were purified⁴ before use.

The apparatus and technique employed in this investigation was the same as described in previous studies⁵.

RESULTS

The halogenation of acetic, propionic, butyric, valeric and caproic acids in chloro, bromo, and nitrobenzene was studied between 20, and 40°C. The second order rate constants are given in Table I.

1. C. N. Hinshelwood and A. R. Legard, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 587.
2. M. A. Beg and H. N. Singh, *Z. Physik. Chemie*, (in press).
3. Hawkins, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1170.
4. Vogel, A. J.; "A text book of Practical Organic Chemistry" Longmans, Green and Co., London, New York, Toronto (1956).
5. M. Aijaz Beg and H. N. Singh, *Z. Physik. Chemie*, 1964, 227, 272.

TABLE I

Second-order rate constants for the different acids in different solvents (taking molar solution of each reactant).

Solvent	Temp., Abs.	Acetic	Propionic	Butyric	Valeric	Caproic
		Acid	Acid	Acid	Acid	Acid
		$k \times 10^6$ mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹				
Chlorobenzene	293	21.1	13.9	13.9	15.8	15.6
	303	36.6	22.2	23.0	26.8	26.3
	313	65.0	36.0	40.0	46.6	46.0
Bromobenzene	293	22.9	15.0	18.5	16.0	16.6
	303	40.0	24.0	30.5	28.7	29.8
	313	72.0	42.5	53.0	50.0	50.6
Nitrobenzene	293	79.0	39.0	45.6	50.0	55.5
	303	149.0	79.3	87.0	90.3	91.3
	313	250.0	139.0	158.6	155.0	155.0

The parameters of the Arrhenius equation, calculated from the data in Table I, along with the previously reported results for acetic and propionic acids in xylene and xylene-dioxane mixture are presented in the following table.

TABLE II

Rate constants and Activation energies for Acetic and Propionic acids in different solvents.

Solvent	Acetic Acid		Propionic Acid	
	$6 + \log K_{30^\circ}$	E. Kcals mole ⁻¹	$6 + \log K_{30^\circ}$	E. Kcals mole ⁻¹
Xylene (dipole moment 2.568)	1.518	12.18	1.452	12.37
75% xylene + 25% dioxane	1.207	12.82	0.943	13.84
50% xylene + 50% dioxane	0.973	13.42	0.766	14.66
25% xylene + 75% dioxane	0.93	13.8	0.695	15.11
Chlorobenzene (dipole moment 1.56)	1.56	11.22	1.346	11.0
Bromobenzene (dipole moment 1.73)	1.60	11.22	1.38	11.45
Nitrobenzene (dipole moment 4.24)	2.173	10.99	1.90	11.22

The parameters of the Eyring equation⁶ based on the data in table I, for acetic, propionic and butyric acids in chloro, bromo, and nitrobenzene, are as follows :

TABLE III
Thermodynamic Functions for the Hologenation of Acetic, Propionic and Butyric acids in different solvents.

Solvent	Acetic Acid			Propionic Acid			Butyric Acid		
	Log P	$\Delta F^\ddagger$ z (313)	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ (313)	Log P	$\Delta F^\ddagger$ z (313)	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ (313)	Log P	$\Delta F^\ddagger$ z (313)	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ (313)
Chloro— Benzene	2.66	24.0 Kcals mole ⁻¹	-42.2 e.u.	2.46	24.2—45.6 Kcals mole ⁻¹	e.u.	2.36	24.3— Kcals mole ⁻¹	44.4 e.u.
Bromo— Benzene	2.90	23.87 Kcals mole ⁻¹	-43.6 e.u.	2.70	24.07—43.6 Kcals mole ⁻¹	e.u.	2.68	23.9— Kcals mole ⁻¹	43.1 e.u.
Nitro— Benzene	4.93	23.11 Kcals mole ⁻¹	-42.0 e.u.	4.66	23.36—42.0 Kcals mole ⁻¹	e.u.	4.68	23.4— Kcals mole ⁻¹	41.4 e.u.

DISCUSSION

The results in table II show that there is no direct relation between the changes in E and the rate from one solvent to another. Fig. 1. is a $\log k$ versus E plot. If changes

FIG. 1

6. Glasston, Eyring and Laidler, "The Theory of Rate Processes", McGraw-Hill Book Company, Inc., New York & London, P. 22 (1941).

in E from one solvent to another were solely responsible for the changes in rate, the points would lie on a line of slope $-2.303 RT$; if changes in P are alone concerned the line would be horizontal⁷. The curve shows that in solvents of low dielectric constant, it is the activation energy of the system which determines the rate. The horizontal part of the curve in Fig. 1 explains that in the solvents of higher dielectric constant, the rate is governed only by P and not by E which has attained a constant value.

Hinshelwood⁷ has pointed out that in some systems the value of P may vary from solvent to solvent, and in favourable circumstances it may be possible to find a series of solvents in which the velocity of a given reaction depends almost entirely on P . The work of Grimm, and Wolf⁸ on Triethyl amine-ethyl iodide reaction supports this view point. Solvent effect on P is all the more pronounced in Pyridine-methyl iodide reaction⁹, where, the relation between the dipole moment of the solvent and the reaction rate is probably through P and not through E , which remains practically constant. Gibbson, Fawcott and Perrin¹⁰ also found an increase in P with increase in rate, inspite of an appreciable increase in the activation energy. In benzoyl chloride-aniline reaction¹¹ also, the increase in rate, with the dipole moment of the medium has been ascribed to increase in P .

Like the formation of quaternary Ammonium salts¹², in thionyl chloride fatty acid reactions, the products are more polar than the reactants. And in this case also, the reaction rate and the probability (P) rise with the dipole moment of the solvent, without causing any perceptible change in the activation energy.

With increase in chain length of the acid, the rate first falls rapidly (from acetic to propionic) and becomes constant oftenwards (vide table I). This is in conformity with the principle that the inductive effect becomes negligible after α -Carbon atom.

A comparison of the thermodynamic functions in chloro-, bromo-, and nitrobenzene for different acids (table III) shows that the internal energy of activation ($\Delta E^\ddagger$), entropy of activation ($\Delta S^\ddagger$) and free energy of activation ($\Delta F^\ddagger$) remain almost unchanged and the rate seems to be only governed by PZ factor of the Arrhenius equation ($k = PZe^{E/RT}$). Lower entropies of activation and high free energies of activation (table III) suggest that the activated complex is not very stable¹³. Therefore, the rate determining step of the reaction appears to be the formation of the activated complex between the reactant molecules. On the basis of our present investigations supported by the previous results (loc. cit.) the following steps can be suggested:

7. N. T. J. Pickles and C. N. Hinshelwood, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1353.
8. G. N. Hinshelwood, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1936, 970.
9. Grimm and Wolf, *Z. Physik. Chemie*, B, 1931, 13, 299.
10. R. A. Fairclough and C. N. Hinshelwood, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1573.
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